

PRESERVE

BLOGPOST 7

Drone Warfare Lessons from the Eastern Mediterranean to Europe's Public Spaces

The Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East has very frequently been the theatre of conflict and hence, also, of display and revealing of relevant systems and technologies. The recent crisis of March 2026, however, offers more than a regional security signal. It entailed a hit on the soil of the EU Member State of Cyprus, therefore posing for Europe a strategic warning. Not so much because exact replication of actors or tactics are expected toward other Member States, but rather because what has fundamentally changed is the drone warfare and drone attack logic, which may now be transposed and transferred to within EU borders, thus blurring the civil – military boundary of security.

The critical tech-&-tactical observations to be made here are not simply about the wider use of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS), but about the fact that aerial threats increasingly come from UAS that are low-cost, scalable, and adaptive. More worryingly: the characteristics observed in areas of military conflict, such as saturation, autonomy, low observability, and economic asymmetry, are those that make drones attractive also for non-state actors, hybrid operations, and terrorist use in civilian contexts and environments.

The recent crisis further underlines the weaponization of UAS and demonstrates how battlefield innovation can turn into civilian vulnerabilities. Drone swarms, wave-based attacks, autonomous navigation, and the use of off-the-shelf components are operational realities, and in fact very 'transferable' to attacks on civilian targets, such as a critical infrastructure node, or a mass event, etc. For European societies, this translates into a growing vulnerability of: mass gatherings (sports events, concerts), critical infrastructures, and even dense urban environments.

In the recent military conflict, one of the most instructive operational lessons, addressing the so-called “asymmetry problem” (i.e. of defending against low-cost threats with high-cost responses), came from the Hellenic Navy’s Frigate HS Psara (F454). What made HS Psara’s response notable was “how” the ship countered the drone threats, which was a combination of: prioritising soft-kill mechanisms (e.g. the “Kentavros/Centaur” Electronic Counter-Measures system) over expensive interceptors and preserving high-value assets for high-value threats, with across-the-board merging of passive detection, layered response, and adaptive decision-making.

Our scope here is of course not of analyzing modern asymmetric naval defensive warfare. It is, however, to investigate whether this paradigm may be transposed to civilian security. The lessons-learned from the operational and tactical deployments, in the recent March 2026 crisis, clearly show that Drone threats are no longer external, isolated, or exceptional, but they are widely systemic, highly adaptive, and increasingly embedded in the broader security landscape. Civilian environments impose additional constraints of: legal and regulatory frameworks, requirements for proportionality and safety, and of course the sheer fact of proximity to populations. For example: in a crowded stadium, a shopping mall, or a city square, the goal is not simply to “neutralise a drone threat”, but to manage the entire ‘threat-lifecycle’ from early indicators to response, without creating cascading or additional risks to citizens.

Therefore, the European response cannot rely on single tools or isolated measures, but it should combine technology, operational doctrine, regulatory coherence, training and coordination. Within this context, the principles underlying the military-defensive approach remain highly relevant then also for civilian security: Intelligence-led anticipation, Early detection without escalation, Layered and proportionate response, as well as Cost-effective and scalable solutions.

This is precisely where the PRESERVE project contributes, by approaching Drone threats as processes that unfold across multiple digital, physical, and operational domains. The PRESERVE system proposes the integrated logic of combining its SECURE, ODIN, and C2 (Command & Control) products as follows:

- SECURE (Swarm-based Counter-UAS Arsenal) Enabling multi-layer detection and response, tailored for complex and scalable threats, including swarms, in operational environments.
- ODIN (Online Drone Intelligence Engine) Extending situational awareness into the digital domain, identifying early indicators of threat preparation across online ecosystems.
- C2 Platform Integrating data, analysis, and operational decision-making into a unified command environment, supporting timely and proportionate responses.

The relevance of this approach becomes particularly clear in civilian contexts, such as a sports stadium with tens of thousands of spectators, a concert venue or open-air festival, a shopping mall or a dense urban neighbourhood. Within the context of such environments, it becomes very critical for security to understand intent, predict behaviour, and rapidly coordinate response across multiple actors. Consequently, these require interoperability between agencies, integration of intelligence and operations, and above all, shared situational awareness.

In other words, what is required is an anticipatory and intelligence-driven protection; a “whole-of-system” approach, consistent with modern European resilience thinking. The PRESERVE project contributes to this effort by translating operational lessons into deployable capabilities, tailored not only for high-intensity counter-UAS scenarios, but also for the protection of everyday public life.

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